

New European Bauhaus Academy

1st New European Bauhaus Academy Conference

Barcelona, February 27, 2026

NEBA North Hub: Co-creating the NEB Across Estonia, Finland and Sweden

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**Circular
Bio-based
Europe**

Joint Undertaking

Co-funded by
the European Union

NEBA North hub

Co-Creating the New European Bauhaus
Across Estonia, Finland and Sweden

European Commission President Ursula von der Leyen and the Prime Ministers of Estonia, Finland and Sweden. September 2021

Founding members

Aalto University (Finland)

Estonian Academy of Arts (Estonia)

Research Institutes of Sweden RISE (Sweden)

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New potential members

Estonian Union of Co-operative Housing Associations (Estonia)

Vilnius Gediminas Technical University (Lithuania)

Norwegian Institute of Wood Technology (Norway)

KTH Royal Institute of Technology (Sweden)

Linnaeus University (Sweden)

FINLAND

Education

Planetary boundaries

Regulatory requirements

Market pull (or resistance)

FINLAND

Education for regulatory needs

Online courses from Aalto University

**Introduction to
Wood Material**
Parts 1-3

**Sustainability
Toolbox**
for building designers

**Climate, Health
and Cities**

Diving into
**radical
creativity**

FINLAND

Education for regulatory needs

Online courses developed by the Ministry of the Environment

Introduction to
decarbonized
construction

Low-carbon
materials in
construction

Whole life
carbon
assessment

Procurement for
Low-Carbon
Construction

Climate benefits
of a building

The arctic
is warming

4x

faster than the
rest of our planet

ESTONIA

Adapting existing Open Academy programmes to NEBA values

EKA avatud akadeemia

Kursused
Koolituslepingu tingimused

Eelakadeemia

Kursused
Koolituslepingu tingimused

Uudised

Kontakt

EKA avatud akadeemia → Erialad → Avatud akadeemia → Ruumiloome ja kestliku elukeskkonna kujundamine

RUUMILOOME JA KESTLIKU ELUKESKKONNA KUJUNDAMINE

David Simi raamatu „Pehme linn” kaanekujundus

Spatial Design and Designing a Sustainable Living Environment
micro-qualification programme

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Kontakt

EKA avatud akadeemia → Erialad → Avatud akadeemia → Linnamaastikud

LINNAMAASTIKUD

Urban Landscapes
micro-qualification programme

ESTONIA

Initiating from short term online trainings to academic deep dives

🕒 3-4

Solutions for renovation supporting sustainability goals, accessibility, and residents' well-being

NEB and circular economy principles for renovation to prolong the lifespan of apartment buildings

Online renovation training by Estonian Union of Co-operative Housing Associations

🕒 240

One semester volumetric renovation and neighbourhood based reconstruction studies in EKA, reviews in Venice Architecture Biennale 2025

ESTONIA

Research and innovation activities

EKA Arh 10 Oct
Conference
2024

BUILDING
SYSTEMS

International research conference in EKA in context of Tallinn Architecture Biennale 2024

SWEDEN

Together

Sweden: Design workshops - Creative North

SWEDEN

Actions

KREATIVA NORRLAND - CREATIVE NORTH

- . 5 different sites
- . Small and medium-sized cities & towns in north Sweden
- . 4-5 on-site learning session
- . 1 online training with theoretical modules
- . Approximately 90 participants so far

SWEDEN

Funding strategy

Funding strategy

Das Triadisches Ballet, 1922

Spring is coming!
(even in north)

